

ISic3681

I.Sicily inscription 3681

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance

found outside the city gate

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Megara Hyblaea, Antiquarium di Megara
Hyblaia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330083

1. Κλεομέδρος.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 330083

Bibliography

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